

In-situ Detection of Active Sites for Carbon-Based Bifunctional Oxygen

Reduction and Evolution Catalysis

Richard W. Haid^{(a),‡}, Regina M. Kluge^{(a),‡}, Thorsten O. Schmidt^(a),

Aliaksandr S. Bandarenka^{(a,b),*}

a - Physik-Department ECS, Technische Universität München, James-Franck-Straße 1, 85748

Garching, Germany

b - Catalysis Research Center TUM, Ernst-Otto-Fischer-Straße 1, 85748 Garching, Germany

‡ - R.W.H. and R.M.K. contributed equally to this work.

* Corresponding author email: bandarenka@ph.tum.de

This document is the submitted Manuscript version of a Published Work that appeared in final form in R.W. Haid, R.M. Kluge, T.O. Schmidt, A.S. Bandarenka. In-situ detection of active sites for carbon-based bifunctional oxygen reduction and evolution catalysis, Electrochimica Acta 382 (2021) 138285. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2021.138285>

Abstract

Due to their availability and electrochemical versatility, carbon-based electrodes are becoming an increasingly popular option as electrocatalysts for fuel cells and metal-air batteries. Additionally, they show great potential as bifunctional catalysts for the oxygen reduction and evolution reaction (ORR/OER) in an alkaline medium. However, to compete with state-of-the-art catalysts, the nature of the active sites and the surface stability under reaction conditions need to be understood in depth. Here, we present a principle study on highly oriented pyrolytic graphite (HOPG), evaluating the surface behavior under both ORR and OER conditions. We use noise analysis in electrochemical scanning tunneling microscopy (n-EC-STM) to monitor and compare ORR and OER active sites with down to atomic resolution. Furthermore, surface degradation can be evaluated during the operation. We find that close to the respective reaction onset, step sites and defects are active for both ORR and OER. Terraces sites are largely inactive and only become involved in the OER at higher potentials. This could imply corrosion of the carbon. However, since the observed surface structures remain unaltered before and after applying the OER in our experiments, we find no clear evidence of surface destruction. These observations can be of fundamental value for the design of carbon-based catalysts as well as carbon support structures, tailoring the surface activity and stability to the dedicated purpose.

Keywords: oxygen evolution reaction, oxygen reduction reaction, carbon catalysts, electrochemical scanning tunneling microscopy, active sites

1. Introduction

Considering the necessary shift in global energy production schemes towards renewable and economical alternatives, there is a specific interest in carbon materials as electrocatalysts for the oxygen reduction and evolution reactions (ORR/OER). Both reactions are fundamental for many types of fuel cells, electrolyzers, and metal-air batteries. Such applications require the use of either a reaction-specific or a bifunctional catalyst [1,2,3,4]. Up to date, state-of-the-art ORR catalysts are based on platinum [5,6], while the most active OER catalysts are oxide materials such as iridium and ruthenium oxide [7,8]. Although those materials show record performances of the respective reactions, they are neither the most cost-effective nor the most sustainable solution. Moreover, these materials have very limited potential as bifunctional catalysts for the ORR and OER [9,10]. As an alternative, carbon-based materials possess many unique qualities that bring them into prominence in various fields of research [11,12,13,14,15]. Their wide availability, conductive properties, and high specific surface area are of interest in electrocatalysis [16,17]. Still, carbon-related materials are in most cases employed as support for metal-based electrocatalysts [18,19,20,21]. However, more recently, studies have shown that doping (with, e.g., nitrogen, sulfur, or boron) and structural modification of the pure carbon lattice can yield higher durability and activities competitive with state-of-the-art precious metal catalysts [15,17,22,23,24,25,26]. Moreover, carbon-based catalysts have been reported as attractive alternatives for individual reactions and as promising bifunctional electrodes [15,23,24,25,26,27]. To make this class of materials competitive in real-world applications, an in-depth understanding of their behavior under reaction conditions is needed.

Here, we use an in-situ characterization technique based on electrochemical scanning tunneling microscopy (EC-STM) to investigate highly oriented pyrolytic graphite (HOPG) in an alkaline medium, which serves as a model system for more advanced carbon-based catalysts and carbon supports [28]. EC-STM combines the mapping of the surface morphology with potential control of the sample. Performing ‘noise’ EC-STM (n-EC-STM) measurements allow monitoring the

local electrochemical activity of surface sites [29,30,31,32,33,34]. This is based on the observation that the local activity of surface sites is directly related to the noise level of the STM signal, which superimposes on the morphology of the sample. In other words, the noise level of the STM signal recorded at the position of active sites is higher than over inactive sites. The origin of this locally confined noise in the STM signal at active sites is the continuous change in the local tunneling medium, i.e., fluctuations in structure and composition of the electrolyte during a reaction. Such fluctuations in the tunneling barrier are known to affect the tunneling current, resulting in visible noise features in the signal [29,33,35,36,37,38].

We demonstrate the capability of the method to investigate the behavior of the HOPG surface under both ORR and OER conditions. The EC-STM technique allows us to observe and compare both reactions at one and the same location on the surface with down to atomic resolution. We obtain essential information on the nature of the active sites for the ORR and OER. Moreover, we monitor the stability of the HOPG surface at different potentials. Concerning the ORR, we find activity exclusively at step edges and defective sites, whereas terrace sites are inactive. This trend is independent of the applied potential and in accordance with the literature [26,39,40,41,42,43]. The OER, however, is more complex and research observations are vague in this aspect [26,44]. In our experiments, we encounter a dependence on the applied potential. At potentials close to the reaction onset, step sites and defects are active for the OER, whereas terrace sites remain largely inactive. At higher potentials, in addition to steps and defects, the terrace sites show an increase in the noise level of the STM signal. This noise level increase implies the participation of the basal plane in the OER. In addition, the noise at terrace sites could also be an indicator of (partial) surface corrosion triggered by the OER. However, we do not find changes in the surface morphology, such as a surface roughening or the introduction of defective sites after the OER. We hope that these observations can help to guide the design of carbon-based catalysts and support structures. Moreover, after

a successful application to a basic model system, we are confident that the n-EC-STM method can be used to analyze more complex bifunctional materials.

2. Experimental Details

The sample material in this study was HOPG purchased from MikroMasch (spread $3.5^{\circ} \pm 1.5^{\circ}$). Before each experiment, a clean graphite surface was ensured by peeling off several surface layers using scotch tape. The n-EC-STM measurements were conducted with a MultiMode scanning probe microscope connected to a NanoScope III scan feedback controller and a Universal Bipotentiostat (Veeco Instruments). The scanning tips were produced in-house by manually ripping a Pt₈₀Ir₂₀ wire (GoodFellow, Ø 0.25mm). The tip is subsequently insulated with Apiezon wax, leaving only a small apex of the tip uncovered to interact with the sample [45]. A miniature electrochemical cell is assembled by mounting the sample between a stainless-steel sample holder and a ring made of polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE), exposing a sample area of 0.28 cm². The cell was filled with electrolyte, in this case, 0.1 M KOH, which was prepared by dissolving KOH pellets (99.99%, Sigma Aldrich) in ultrapure water (18.2 MΩ) from an Evoqua Ultra Clear 10TWF 30 UV (Evoqua, Germany) water purification system. Due to the small dimensions of the cell, conventional reference electrodes are impractical, and therefore, a Pt wire (MaTecK, Ø 0.5mm, 99.99% purity) was used for this purpose. This Pt-quasi reference electrode has been established as a reliable alternative for EC-STM purposes [29,30,31,32,33,34]. The reference electrode will be referred to in the index of the potential values as 'V_{Pt}'. As the counter electrode, a graphite rod (Goodfellow, Ø 0.5mm, 99.95% purity) was chosen. Using the same material for counter and working electrode minimizes the risk of introducing impurities to the system, which could alter the electrocatalytic properties. The experiments were conducted at ambient temperature, and the whole set-up was exposed to air at all times. A list of the experimental parameters is given in Table S1 of the Supporting

Information. The WSxM 5.0 Develop 9.1 software was used to analyze the data [46]. The sketch in Figure 1 was created with the Autodesk Fusion 360 software.

The objective of the n-EC-STM method is to identify active sites under an applied sample potential. The sample potential can be chosen such that a reaction is occurring ('on') or hindered ('off'). The illustrations in Figures 1a and b clarify the difference between these two situations. In case the reactions are 'off' (Figure 1a), the STM traces the surface structure with a stable signal. When a reaction is 'on' (Figure 1b), the STM signal at active areas shows a considerable (locally confined) noise level. In the sketch, the active sites are exemplarily located at the step edge and distinguish themselves by noise spikes under reaction 'on' conditions. The origin of the noise under reaction conditions can be traced back to the sensitivity of the tunneling current on the composition of the tunneling barrier [35,36,37,47]. An ongoing reaction will change the composition and structure of the electrolyte and will thus lead to continuous changes in the tunneling barrier. It has been reported in the literature that such changes in the electrolyte result in a 'noisy' signal [29,33,35,36,37,38]. As a consequence, the noise is the most pronounced at the location of the reaction, i.e., the active sites.

3. Results

In this work, the n-EC-STM method was applied to HOPG under both oxygen reduction and evolution conditions in a 0.1 M KOH solution. The technique is capable of identifying active sites by their higher noise level in the STM signal compared to inactive sites. More details on the working principle are given in section 2. To assess the active centers, the STM signal of the surface when no reaction takes place ('off') is compared to the signal when a reaction takes place (OER or ORR 'on'). In order to select the corresponding sample potentials, a typical cyclic voltammogram (CV) of the freshly prepared HOPG surface was recorded in the EC-STM cell and is shown in Figure 2a. For reaction 'off', we choose a potential of 0 V_{Pt}, where the net current is zero. Towards negative potentials, the ORR takes place. For our experiments, we

choose two different potentials in this region: A potential near the onset of the reaction ($-0.3 V_{Pt}$, ORR_{-0.3}, red) and a potential at a higher sample current ($-0.6 V_{Pt}$, ORR_{-0.6}, dark red). At positive potentials, the OER takes place. Here, we set three levels of potential: low potential ($0.3 V_{Pt}$, OER_{0.3}, light green), medium potential ($0.6 V_{Pt}$, OER_{0.6}, green), and high potential ($0.9 V_{Pt}$, OER_{0.9}, dark green). Potentials leading to higher sample currents in both directions were avoided due to the possible destructive effect on the sample and the scanning tip. Besides, excessive bubble formation during the OER will cause the STM probe to disengage from the surface.

Figure 2b shows an n-EC-STM measurement across a step edge with respect to the selected potentials. The experiments were conducted in constant current mode; a list of the most essential parameters of all the n-EC-STM measurements can be found in Table S1 of the Supporting Information. Comparing the STM signal for reaction ‘on’ and ‘off’, the active sites of each reaction can be identified by their higher noise level. Under ORR conditions (red color shades), the upper edge of the step exhibits distinct spikes in the STM signal. In contrast, the terrace sites yield a stable STM signal comparable to reaction ‘off’. This leads to the conclusion that the upper edge of the steps is active towards the ORR, whereas terrace sites remain inactive. It is noteworthy that, in general, the noise level (the height and density of the spikes) at active sites is more pronounced at higher sample currents. This is understandable since an increased reaction rate leads to stronger fluctuations in the tunneling medium and thus noise in the signal [33]. Moving towards the OER (green color shades) again leads to a significant increase in the noise level at the upper step edge. Moreover, terrace sites start to exhibit noise features at the highest applied potential for the OER (dark green, $0.9 V_{Pt}$).

Note that the same experiment was repeated in $0.1 M HClO_4$ to confirm that the increase in the noise level indeed stems from the electrocatalytic activity and not from, e.g., a measurement artifact. In an acidic medium, no reaction takes place in the potential range from -0.6 to $+0.9$

V_{Pt} . As visible in Figure S1 of the Supporting Information, no noise was observed under these conditions.

Our findings are expanded upon in Figure 3, where a distinct surface area was imaged multiple times under the application of different potentials: First under ORR conditions (a and b), then while the reactions are ‘off’ (c), under OER conditions (d and e) and finally going back to the ORR (f). In these images, four step edges, as well as some defective sites along the left step-edge, are mapped. It should be noted that the changing rotation of the surface features throughout Figure 3 can be ascribed to thermal drift common to STM measurements at room temperature. In Figure 3g, height profiles at roughly the same position from each sub-image are given. The positions of these line scans are marked with black dotted lines in Figures 3a-f. The active sites at each potential can be identified by comparison to the structure while the reactions are ‘off’ in Figure 3c. Under reaction conditions, a high noise level can be identified by a brighter intensity in the STM image and spikes in the height profile given in Figure 3g. In Figure 3a, ORR_{-0.6}, we find noise features along the upper edge of the steps and at defect sites. This is in line with the previous measurement in Figure 2b. Terrace sites show no noise. For ORR_{-0.3} in Figure 3b, the activity at the step sites and defects diminishes, albeit not subsiding completely. Terrace sites exhibit no activity under the applied ORR conditions. In Figure 3c, reaction ‘off’, the surface morphology is mapped with a noise-free signal. In the next step, the potential was set to the OER. As visible in Figure 3d, OER_{0.3}, and the corresponding line scan in 3g, the steps and defects exhibit the first activity indications, whereas terrace sites show no noise. In Figure 3e, OER_{0.6}, the noise level of these sites grows stronger. Notably, the noise also extends to the terraces. Due to the involvement of the terrace sites already at this potential, we avoid the highest potential level OER_{0.9}, to prevent surface degradation. Instead, we return to the ORR_{-0.6} to examine the effect of the OER conditions on the surface quality and the ORR activity. As Figure 3f, ORR_{-0.6}, reveals, step sites are active, and terrace sites are inactive. Comparing this to Figure 3a, the surface behavior at this potential before and after OER is

evidently unchanged. Since defective terrace sites would be active for the ORR, no noise at the terraces suggests that no defects were created during the OER. Consequently, we can assume that the surface quality is not significantly reduced by the oxygen evolution in this experiment. After establishing the capability of the n-EC-STM technique to evaluate bifunctional catalyst surfaces, we demonstrate the high-resolution imaging of the active sites. This requires the constant height mode with a relatively low set-point and fast scanning speed of the STM probe. Furthermore, the feedback loop is disabled for these measurements. Due to these challenging requirements, we refrain from investigating the OER and focus instead on the ORR. Figures 4a and b show the identical position of a step (indicated by the dotted white line) recorded at two different potentials ($-0.5 V_{Pt}$ and $-0.7 V_{Pt}$). In these atomically resolved images, we identify active sites mainly within the first five rows of atoms at the upper edge of the step. We can also see that there are different types of active sites at steps, which contribute to the reaction at different potentials. This is in line with the findings of the measurements in Figures 3a and b where we observe that there are more active sites along the step edge at higher sample currents. Here, we can distinguish them with high resolution. For example, the site indicated as ‘ α ’ in Figure 4 is already active at $-0.5 V_{Pt}$, while the site ‘ β ’ shows no signs of activity at this point. At $-0.7 V_{Pt}$, this site becomes active as well. This is also illustrated by the height profiles along the black line, shown below the respective images. While the tip traces the pure surface structure at $-0.5 V_{Pt}$, there is a clear spike in the signal over the active site under the application of $-0.7 V_{Pt}$. The images shown in Figure 4 were filtered using the fast Fourier transformation (FFT) tool. The as-recorded images, as well as additional high-resolution images, are provided in Figure S2.

4. Discussion

Using n-EC-STM, we investigate the nature of active sites for ORR and OER on a HOPG surface. Concerning the ORR, we conclude that it is exclusively catalyzed at step edges and defective sites. This is in line with previous studies and is likely to originate from the various

types of sites at steps with different binding energies towards the reaction intermediates [26,39,40,41,42,43,48,49]. Besides the step sites, these images also corroborate the notion that the basal plane is largely inactive during the ORR [39,40,41,42,49] since there is no noise on the terraces. Furthermore, the atomically resolved images in Figure 4 suggest that the active sites are confined to a few rows of atoms at the upper edge of the steps, implying that the lower layer of graphene does not influence the activity. This could be interesting for catalysts based on lower dimensional structures like graphene and nanotubes. Terrace sites do not appear to play a role regarding the ORR. Therefore, to tune the activity of carbon catalyst or carbon-support structures, adjusting the ratio of steps and defects to terraces could be an appropriate tool.

Under OER conditions, we notice that close to the reaction onset step and defect sites are active. Towards higher potentials, the terraces also exhibit noise. However, the exact value of the potential where this ‘transition’ happens is not constant. First of all, the potential of the Pt-quasi-reference electrode is not absolutely defined. Keeping in mind the shape of the CV in Figure 2a, we could speculate that the activity on the terraces coincides with and is connected to the notable increase in the OER current. Due to the stability issues connected to the OER [26,44,50,51,52,53], it is reasonable to presume that this activity is accompanied by surface corrosion. However, as defects are active towards the ORR [26,40,41,43,54], we should see an increased activity when going back to ORR conditions. This is not the case, so we can assume that the surface is not or not substantially affected by the OER conditions applied in these experiments.

Naturally, surface stability is a vital aspect of a bifunctional catalyst. Our experiments indicate adequate stability of the graphene surface under ORR conditions and at lower OER potentials. Towards higher OER potentials, the surface stability is more questionable. Since in our experiment the surface quality seemed unaffected, we assume commensurate stability of the surface. Certainly, increasing the potential further would ultimately result in surface

destruction. However, our measurements suggest there could be a sweet spot where the entire surface is active while the surface quality is not yet negatively affected.

5. Conclusion

Using HOPG in an alkaline medium as a model system, we investigated the behavior of terraces, steps, and defects under ORR and OER conditions. With the n-EC-STM technique, we can detect and directly compare their location in-situ on the surface under ORR and OER conditions, respectively. For both reactions, the most active sites are located on the upper edge of steps and at defective sites. In the case of the ORR, the terraces show no signs of activity, even at higher sample currents. For the OER, on the other hand, the terraces become involved when a certain potential is exceeded, indicated by an increased noise level across the entire sample surface. Subsequent measurements during the ORR did not indicate a significantly changed behavior or morphology of the surface. Therefore, we can assume that the surface condition was largely unaffected by the previously applied OER conditions. Finally, we visualize a step with atomic resolution and examine the role of the ORR active centers with increasing potential. We recommend that these results are applied as guidelines for a smart design of carbon-based catalysts and support materials.

Acknowledgements

RMK, RWH and ASB acknowledge the financial support from German Research Foundation (DFG) under Grant No. 355784621, under Germany's Excellence Strategy–EXC 2089/1–390776260, under Germany's Excellence cluster 'e-conversion' and DFG projects BA 5795/4-1, BA 5795/5-1, and BA 5795/6-1. TOS and ASB acknowledge funding provided from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement HERMES No 952184.

Supplementary data

Supplementary data is provided with the manuscript.

Figures

Figure 1. Model of the n-EC-STM working principle on HOPG. a) If the reactions are switched ‘off’, the STM gives a map of the surface with a stable, noise-free signal. b) Under reaction conditions (reaction ‘on’), the STM signal is locally destabilized by reaction processes at active sites. In this example, the step is the most active area as recognizable by the spikes in the recorded signal.

Figure 2. a) CV of the HOPG surface in 0.1 M KOH recorded in the EC-STM cell (50 mVs^{-1} scan rate), against a Pt quasi-reference and in the air (see section 2 for more details). We assign a potential of 0 V_{Pt} to reaction ‘off’ for the n-EC-STM measurements since the corresponding current is zero. For both ORR and OER, we select several potentials which are indicated by bars of red and green color shades, respectively. b) n-EC-STM of a step edge. The sample potential was varied from ORR ‘on’ (red shades) to reaction ‘Off’ (blue) and OER ‘on’ (green shades) conditions. The STM signal of the step sites shows a high noise level for both OER and ORR ‘on’. The terrace sites, on the other hand, do not exhibit noise features for the ORR and the OER at low and medium potentials. At the highest applied OER potential ($0.9 \text{ V}_{\text{Pt}}$), the terrace sites exhibit some spikes in the STM signal as well, however still less pronounced than at step sites.

Figure 3. n-EC-STM measurements at different levels of potential probing both the ORR and OER at the same surface area. In this area, in total four step edges and several defect sites can be seen as marked in the images. The defects are most pronounced along the left-most step edge. Active sites can be identified by their brighter intensity in the STM image compared to the reaction ‘off’ image given in c. a) For ORR-0.6, the upper edges of steps, as well as defects, exhibit noise features. The STM signal of the terrace sites is stable. b) For ORR-0.3, less step sites show noise features compared to ORR-0.6. c) For reaction ‘off’, the morphology of the surface is mapped without noise features, showing clearly four steps and a few defect sites along the left-most step edge. d) For OER_{0.3}, a few sites along the step edges, including defects, show noise. e) For OER_{0.6}, more step sites show noise compared to OER_{0.3}. Furthermore, the noise extends to the terraces. f) When returning to the ORR-0.6, we observe no significant changes in the surface structure compared to the start of the measurement at the same potential given in a. g) For each applied potential, a height profile is extracted at approximately the same position (marked by a black dotted line in each STM image). Active sites can be readily identified by the spikes in the signal.

Figure 4. High-resolution n-EC-STM measurement of a step (white dotted line) under ORR conditions. a) At a potential of $-0.5 V_{Pt}$, only a few sites at the step, e.g., site ‘ α ’ are already active, while the majority, e.g., ‘ β ’ is not yet active. b) At a sample potential of $-0.7 V_{Pt}$, more sites, such as ‘ β ’, become active. Line-scans marked by the black line are given below the respective image and elucidate the peak in the STM signal over an active site. Both images are FFT filtered; the as-recorded images can be found in Figure S2 of the Supporting Information.

References

- [1] I. Katsounaros, S. Cherevko, A. R. Zeradjanin, K. J. J. Mayrhofer, Oxygen Electrochemistry as a Cornerstone for Sustainable Energy Conversion, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 53 (2014) 102.
- [2] I. E. L. Stephens, A. S. Bondarenko, U. Grønbjerg, J. Rossmeisl, I. Chorkendorff, Oxygen Electrochemistry as a Cornerstone for Sustainable Energy Conversion, *Energy Environ. Sci.* 5 (2012) 6744.
- [3] H. Dau, C. Limberg, T. Reier, M. Risch, S. Roggan, P. Strasser, The Mechanism of Water Oxidation: From Electrolysis via Homogeneous to Biological Catalysis, *ChemCatChem* 2 (2010) 724.
- [4] M. Tahir, L. Pan, F. Idrees, X. Zhang, L. Wang, J.-J. Zou, Z. L. Wang, Electrocatalytic oxygen evolution reaction for energy conversion and storage: A comprehensive review, *Nano Energy* 27 (2017) 136.
- [5] V. R. Stamenkovic, B. Fowler, B. S. Mun, G. Wang, P. N. Ross, C. A. Lucas, N. M. Marković, Improved Oxygen Reduction Activity on Pt₃Ni(111) via Increased Surface Site Availability, *Science* 315 (2007) 493.
- [6] J. Greeley, I. E. L. Stephens, A. S. Bondarenko, T. P. Johansson, H. A. Hansen, T. F. Jaramillo, J. Rossmeisl, I. Chorkendorff, J. K. Norskov, Alloys of platinum and early transition metals as oxygen reduction electrocatalysts, *Nat. Chem.* 1 (2009) 552.
- [7] S. Trasatti, Electrocatalysis by oxides—attempt at a unifying approach, *J. Electroanal. Chem.* 111 (1980) 125.
- [8] K. A. Stoerzinger, L. Qiao, M. D. Biegalski, Y. Shao-Horn, Orientation-Dependent Oxygen Evolution Activities of Rutile IrO₂ and RuO₂, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* 5 (2014) 1636.
- [9] L. Han, Y. Sun, S. Li, C. Cheng, C. E. Halbig, P. Feicht, J. L. Hübner, P. Strasser, S. Eigler, In-Plane Carbon Lattice-Defect Regulating Electrochemical Oxygen Reduction to Hydrogen Peroxide Production over Nitrogen-Doped Graphene, *ACS Catal.* 9 (2019) 1283.

-
- [10] J. Pakrash, H. Joachin, Electrocatalytic activity of ruthenium for oxygen reduction in alkaline solution, *Electrochim. Acta* 45 (2000) 2289.
- [11] Y. Shao, J. Wang, H. Wu, J. Liu, I. Aksay, Y. Lin, Graphene Based Electrochemical Sensors and Biosensors: A Review, *Electroanalysis* 22 (2010) 1027.
- [12] R. K. Roy, K.-R. Lee, Biomedical Applications of Diamond-Like Carbon Coatings: A Review, *Biomed. Mater. Res.* 83B (2007) 72.
- [13] X. Li, J. Yu, S. Wageh, A. A. Al-Ghamdi, J. Xie, Graphene in Photocatalysis: A Review, *Small* 12 (2016) 6640.
- [14] D. Higgins, P. Zamani, A. Yu, Z. Chen, The application of graphene and its composites in oxygen reduction electrocatalysis: a perspective and review of recent progress, *Energy Environ. Sci.* 9 (2016) 357.
- [15] J. Duan, S. Chen, M. Jaroniec, S. Z. Qiao, Heteroatom-Doped Graphene-Based Materials for Energy-Relevant Electrocatalytic Processes, *ACS Catal.* 5 (2015) 5207.
- [16] D. A. C. Brownson, D. K. Kampouris, C. E. Banks, Graphene electrochemistry: fundamental concepts through to prominent applications, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 41 (2012) 6944.
- [17] A. Ambrosi, C. K. Chua, N. M. Latiff, A. H. Loo, C. H. A. Wong, A. Y. S. Eng, A. Bonanni, M. Pumera, Graphene and its electrochemistry – an update, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 45 (2016) 2458.
- [18] B. Garlyyev, S. Watzele, J. Fichtner, J. Michalička, A. Schökel, A. Senyshyn, A. Perego, D. Pan, H. A. El-Sayed, J. M. Macak, P. Atanassov, I. V. Zenyuk, A. S. Bandarenka, Electrochemical top-down synthesis of C-supported Pt nano-particles with controllable shape and size: Mechanistic insights and application, *Nano Res.* (2020) <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12274-020-3281-z>.
- [19] S. Sui, X. Wang, X. Zhou, Y. Su, S. Riffat, C.-j. Liu, A comprehensive review of Pt electrocatalysts for the oxygen reduction reaction: Nanostructure, activity, mechanism and carbon support in PEM fuel cells, *J. Mater. Chem. A* 5 (2017) 1808.

-
- [20] F. H. B. Lima, J. F. R. de Castro, L. G. R. A. Santos, E. A. Ticianelli, Electrocatalysis of oxygen reduction on carbon-supported Pt–Co nanoparticles with low Pt content, *J. Power Sources* 190 (2009) 293.
- [21] M. Bernt, A. Siebel, H. A. Gasteiger, Analysis of Voltage Losses in PEM Water Electrolyzers with Low Platinum Group Metal Loadings, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 165 (2018) F305.
- [22] Z. Sun, J. Masa, P. Weide, S. M. Fairclough, A. W. Robertson, P. Ebbinghaus, J. H. Warner, S. C. E. Tsang, M. Muhler, W. Schuhmann, High-quality functionalized few-layer graphene: facile fabrication and doping with nitrogen as a metal-free catalyst for the oxygen reduction reaction, *J. Mater. Chem. A* 3 (2015) 15444.
- [23] K. Qu, Y. Zheng, S. Dai, S. Z. Qiao, Graphene oxide-polydopamine derived N, S-codoped carbon nanosheets as superior bifunctional electrocatalysts for oxygen reduction and evolution, *Nano Energy* 19 (2016) 373.
- [24] G.-L. Tian, M.-Q. Zhao, D. Yu, X.-Y. Kong, J.-Q. Huang, Q. Zhang, F. Wei, Nitrogen-Doped Graphene/Carbon Nanotube Hybrids: In Situ Formation on Bifunctional Catalysts and Their Superior Electrocatalytic Activity for Oxygen Evolution/Reduction Reaction, *Small* 10 (2014) 2251.
- [25] J. Maruyama, S. Maruyama, T. Fukuhara, H. Mizuhata, S. Takenaka, A. Yoshida, K. Miyazaki, Bifunctional Oxygen Electrodes with Highly Step-Enriched Surface of Fe–N x Containing Carbonaceous Thin Film, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 167 (2020) 060504.
- [26] Y. Jia, L. Zhang, A. Du, G. Gao, J. Chen, X. Yan, C. L. Brown, X. Yao, Defect Graphene as a Trifunctional Catalyst for Electrochemical Reactions, *Adv. Mater.* 28 (2016) 9532.
- [27] J.-C. Li, P.-X. Hou, S.-Y. Zhao, C. Liu, D.-M. Tang, M. Cheng, F. Zeng, H.-M. Cheng, A 3D bi-functional porous N-doped carbon microtube sponge electrocatalyst for oxygen reduction and oxygen evolution reactions, *Energy Environ. Sci.* 9 (2016) 3079.
- [28] A. K. Geim, K. S. Novoselov, The rise of graphene, *Nat. Mater.* 6 (2007) 183.

-
- [29] J. H. K. Pfisterer, Y. Liang, O. Schneider, A. S. Bandarenka, Direct instrumental identification of catalytically active surface sites, *Nature* 549 (2017), 74.
- [30] Y. Liang, C. Csoklich, D. McLaughlin, O. Schneider, A. S. Bandarenka, Revealing Active Sites for Hydrogen Evolution at Pt and Pd Atomic Layers on Au Surfaces, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 11 (2019) 12476.
- [31] Y. Liang, D. McLaughlin, C. Csoklich, O. Schneider, A. S. Bandarenka, The nature of active centers catalyzing oxygen electro-reduction at platinum surfaces in alkaline media, *Energy Environ. Sci.* 12 (2019) 351.
- [32] E. Mitterreiter, Y. Liang, M. Golibrzuch, D. McLaughlin, C. Csoklich, J. D. Bartl, A. Holleitner, U. Wurstbauer, A. S. Bandarenka, In-situ visualization of hydrogen evolution sites on helium ion treated molybdenum dichalcogenides under reaction conditions, *npj 2D Mater. Appl.* 3 (2019) 25.
- [33] R. W. Haid, R. M. Kluge, Y. Liang, A. S. Bandarenka, In Situ Quantification of the Local Electrocatalytic Activity via Electrochemical Scanning Tunneling Microscopy, *Small Methods* (2020) 2000710.
- [34] R. M. Kluge, R. W. Haid, A. S. Bandarenka, Assessment of Active Areas for the Oxygen Evolution Reaction on an Amorphous Iridium Oxide Surface, *J. Catal.* (2021), *accepted*.
- [35] J. Halbritter, G. Repphun, S. Vinzelberg, G. Staikov, W. J. Lorenz, Tunneling mechanisms in electrochemical STM —distance and voltage tunneling spectroscopy, *Electrochim. Acta* 40 (1995) 1385.
- [36] M. Hugelmann, W. Schindler, Tunnel barrier height oscillations at the solid/liquid interface, *Surf. Sci.* 541 (2003) L643.
- [37] M. Hugelmann, W. Schindler, A. S. Bandarenka, In Situ Distance Tunneling Spectroscopy at Au(111)/0.02 M HClO₄, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 151 (2004) E97.

-
- [38] F. C. Simeone, D. M. Kolb, S. Venkatachalam, T. Jacob, The Au(111)/Electrolyte Interface: A Tunnel-Spectroscopic and DFT Investigation, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 46 (2007) 8903.
- [39] A. Shen, Y. Zou, Q. Wang, R. A. W. Dryfe, X. Huang, S. Dou, L. Dai, S. Wang, Oxygen Reduction Reaction in a Droplet on Graphite: Direct Evidence that the Edge Is More Active than the Basal Plane, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 53 (2014) 10804.
- [40] C. Tang, Q. Zhang, Nanocarbon for Oxygen Reduction Electrocatalysis: Dopants, Edges, and Defects, *Adv. Mater.* 29 (2017) 1604103.
- [41] L. Zhang, Q. Xu, J. Niu, Z. Xia, Role of lattice defects in catalytic activities of graphene clusters for fuel cells, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 17 (2015) 16733.
- [42] L. Tao, Q. Wang, S. Dou, Z. Ma, J. Huo, S. Wang, L. Dai, Edge-rich and dopant-free graphene as a highly efficient metal-free electrocatalyst for the oxygen reduction reaction, *Chem. Commun.* 52 (2016) 2764.
- [43] Y. Jiang, L. Yang, T. Sun, J. Zhao, Z. Lyu, O. Zhuo, X. Wang, Q. Wu, J. Ma, Z. Hu, Significant Contribution of Intrinsic Carbon Defects to Oxygen Reduction Activity, *ACS Catal.* 5 (2015) 6707.
- [44] Y. Lin, Q. Lu, F. Song, L. Yu, A. K. Mechler, R. Schlögl, S. Heumann, Oxygen Evolution Reaction at Carbon Edge Sites: Investigation of Activity Evolution and Structure–Function Relationships with Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 58 (2019) 8917.
- [45] L. A. Nagahara, T. Thundat, S. M. Lindsay, Preparation and characterization of STM tips for electrochemical studies, *Rev. Sci. Instrum.* 60 (1989) 3128.
- [46] I. Horcas, R. Fernández, J. M. Gómez-Rodríguez, J. Colchero, J. Gómez-Herrero, A. M. Baro, WSXM: A software for scanning probe microscopy and a tool for nanotechnology, *Rev. Sci. Instrum.* 78 (2007) 13705.
- [47] G. Engelmann, J. Ziegler, D. Kolb, Electrochemical fabrication of large arrays of metal nanoclusters, *Surface Science* 401 (1998) L420-L424.

-
- [48] Z. Yang, Z. Yao, G. Li, G. Fang, H. Nie, Z. Liu, X. Zhou, X. Chen, S. Huang, Sulfur-Doped Graphene as an Efficient Metal-free Cathode Catalyst for Oxygen Reduction, *ACS Nano* 6 (2012) 205.
- [49] T. J. Davies, M. E. Hyde, R. G. Compton, Nanotrench Arrays Reveal Insight into Graphite Electrochemistry, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 44 (2005) 5121.
- [50] S. Trasatti, Electrocatalysis in the anodic evolution of oxygen and chlorine, *Electrochim. Acta* 29 (1984) 1503.
- [51] C. Spöri, J. T. H. Kwan, A. Bonkdarpour, D. P. Wilkinson, P. Strasser, The Stability Challenges of Oxygen Evolving Catalysts: Towards a Common Fundamental Understanding and Mitigation of Catalyst Degradation, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 56 (2017) 5994.
- [52] C. C. L. McCrory, S. Jung, J. C. Peters, T. F. Jaramillo, Benchmarking Heterogeneous Electrocatalysts for the Oxygen Evolution Reaction, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 135 (2013) 16977.
- [53] I. Alex, W.-J. Orawan, M. Douglas R., On the Stability of Water Oxidation Catalysts: Challenges and Prospects, *Aust. J. Chem.* 65 (2012) 638.
- [54] J. C. Byers, A. G. Güell, P. R. Unwin, Nanoscale Electrocatalysis: Visualizing Oxygen Reduction at Pristine, Kinked, and Oxidized Sites on Individual Carbon Nanotubes, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 136 (2014) 11252.

In-situ Evaluation of Active Sites for Carbon-Based Bifunctional Oxygen Reduction and Evolution Catalysis

Supporting Information

Richard W. Haid^{(a),‡}, Regina M. Kluge^{(a),‡}, Thorsten O. Schmidt^(a), Aliaksandr S.

Bandarenka^{(a,b),*}

a - Physik-Department ECS, Technische Universität München, James-Franck-Straße 1, 85748 Garching, Germany

b - Catalysis Research Center TUM, Ernst-Otto-Fischer-Straße 1, 85748 Garching, Germany

‡ - R.W.H. and R.M.K. contributed equally to this work.

* Corresponding author email: bandarenka@ph.tum.de

Contents

1. Experimental parameters of the n-EC-STM measurements
2. Equivalent n-EC-STM measurement in 0.1 M HClO₄
3. Additional images and details of the high-resolution measurements

1. Experimental parameters of the n-EC-STM measurements

Table S1. Parameters used while capturing the n-EC-STM measurements.

	Mode	Tip setpoint*	Tip potential
Fig. 2b	Constant current	1.0 nA	0.00 V _{Pt}
Fig. 3	Constant current	2.0 nA	-0.05 V _{Pt}
Fig. 4	Constant height	2.0 nA	-0.05 V _{Pt}
Fig. S1b	Constant current	2.0 nA	-0.05 V _{Pt}
Fig. S2c	Constant height	2.0 nA	-0.05 V _{Pt}
Fig. S2d	Constant height	0.5 nA	-0.05 V _{Pt}

*In the MultiMode (Veeco Instruments), the setpoint is always given in nA, regardless of the selected scanning mode.

2. Equivalent n-EC-STM measurement in 0.1 M HClO₄

Fig. S1. c) Cyclic Voltammogram of HOPG in 0.1 M HClO₄ in the EC-STM cell (50 mV/s scan rate, exposed to air). In the potential range of -0.6 V_{Pt} to 0.9 V_{Pt}, that was used throughout this study, no reactions should be catalyzed (contrary to the measurements in KOH). Consequently, we should see no noise in the n-EC-STM measurements under these conditions. Indeed, as b) shows, we do not see any noise under these potentials, neither at steps nor at terraces. We can therefore exclude that the noise in the n-EC-STM measurements is an artefact.

3. Additional images and details of the high-resolution measurements

Fig. S2. a) and b) are the unfiltered images of the ones shown in Fig. 4. c) High resolution image of a very unregular step at $-0.4 V_{Pt}$. The inset shows line scans across an active (red line) and an inactive (black line) step site. In d) an area with multiple steps was captured at $-0.5 V_{Pt}$. Active sites (white dots) are dispersed along the steps, while the terraces are inactive. e) and f) are the unfiltered versions of c) and d).